

it by its first Name and the Natives by the last ”
(I, 350).

It is, of course, quite true that Mahomet and Maḥmūd are different names, and that thus this “ Mahomet Bander ” is not necessarily to be identified with the mint-town Maḥmūd Bandar. But it would be surprising if the distinction between the two names had been observed by Hamilton, a rough, plain-spoken “ Captain ”, who by his own telling was at Madras officially declared “ a rank Pirate ”. He disavows any claim to exact scholarship. “ We Britains, who either go voluntarily or are sent to Neptune’s Schools in our Youth, to learn Politeness and Eloquence, very rarely meet with Apollo’s bright Sons or Disciples to instruct us in the knowledge of Languages.” He openly admits that what he has recorded in his book “ came posting through a weak and treacherous Memory with little Elegancy.” It thus may well be that on occasion his memory played him false, and that from this cause he has handed down in a form slightly altered a name that originally read Maḥmūd Bandar.

BOMBAY :

GEO P. TAYLOR.

21st May, 1910.

86. ON THE SYMBOL ‘ ŠĀHĪB QIRĀN.’

It is well known that the ‘*alāmat* Šāḥib Qirān is present as a royal title on many of the coins of the Mughal Emperors of India, and it may be helpful to have on record just when and where and by whom this title was used. But first a word as to its meaning. The term *qirān*, *قران*, indicates in the astrology of Persia a conjunction of two or more planets. Now not all conjunctions are held to be auspicious, for while some planets, such as Venus and Jupiter, are supposed to shed a beneficent influence, others, such as Mars and Saturn, are deemed to exert a malignant power. A pair of planets, each of good omen, is expressed in Arabic by the dual *سعدین*, *sa’dain*, but if the two import bad luck the term employed is *نحسین* *nahsain*. Hence the full form *قران سعدین* means definitely an auspicious conjunction, but *قران نحسین* a conjunction as definitely inauspicious. It would seem, however, that *قران* when used absolutely can carry with it *سعدین* understood, and accordingly it admits of interpretation as a conjunction presaging happiness.¹ By consequence the title Šāḥib Qirān comes to

¹ As is well known, “ the horned moon with one bright star ” is at the present day the felicitous emblem of the ‘ Öthmānlī Sultāns of

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mean 'Lord of the (happy) conjunction,' whence arose the derivative meanings, 'a favourite of Fortune,' 'a great Emperor,' 'a Kaiser,' 'an Augustus.'

Tamerlane is said to have been the first monarch to have borne this title, but the epithet has not been found on his coins. The late M. Ed. Drouin in his paper on "Les Symboles astrologiques sur les monnaies de la Perse" mentions that Tīmūr in his desire to foster the prosperity of his capital city Samarqand invited thither astrologers and other men of learning. During his reign (A.H. 771-807) a remarkable planetary conjunction took place, and the astrologers, availing themselves of the occasion, fashioned as an adulatory tribute to their imperial patron the title *Ṣāhib Qirān*. Inasmuch as the celestial phenomenon then observed recurs but once in thirty years, they foretold that Tīmūr's reign would last for at least that period of time, and as a matter of fact it did cover the thirty-five years from 1369 till 1404. The title thus assigned to Tīmūr seems to have become for a while a term distinctive of that Emperor. The *Tūzuk-i-Jahāngīrī* expressly states:

"In these Memoirs whenever *Ṣāhib Qirānī* is written it refers to Amīr Tīmūr Gūrgān."³

In the Preface to the Persian translation of the *Mulfūzāt-i-Tīmūrī* the translator, Abū Ṭālib Ḥusainī, says:

"I saw in the library of Ja'far, Governor of Yaman, a book in the Turkī language, dictated by His Majesty who now dwells in Paradise, *Ṣāhib Qirānī*."²

In Jahāngīr's time the Royal Signet of the Great Mughal bore, inscribed in the topmost of its nine circles, the words:

امیر تیمور صاحب قران

None of Tīmūr's successors on the throne of Samarqand bore the title of *Ṣāhib Qirān*, but in that later Empire of the Great Mughals, founded in Hindūstān by Bābar, sixth in descent from Tīmūr, the coins of no less than nine of the Emperors (or Claimants to the throne) exhibit the title either

Turkey. Its origin dates so far back as B.C. 339. In that year Philip of Macedon, while besieging Byzantium, attempted in the early night hours an escalade of the city; but it is said a sudden silver gleam flashing from the western sky revealed the advancing enemy, and thus Byzantium was saved. In commemoration of the Divine aid so wonderfully vouchsafed, it was forthwith decreed that the city's badge should be a crescent, its light reinforced by a star, and that both star and crescent should be graven on the city's coins. This emblem was adopted by the Turks after Constantinople fell to Muḥammad II in 1453, and since then it has come to be popularly regarded as the distinctive symbol of Islām. To the Muḥammadans of India, however, it is a foreign ensign, in no way associated with their religion.

¹ The *Tūzuk-i-Jahāngīrī*, translated by Rogers and Beveridge, page 5.

² The *Mulfūzāt Tīmūrī*, translated by Stewart, page 1.

unchanged or in a slightly varied form. The nine Emperors are—

Shāh Jahān I, Shāh Shujā', Murād Bakhsh,
Shāh 'Ālam Bahādur I, Jahāndār, Farrukh-siyar,
Muhammad Shāh, Shāh 'Ālam II, and Akbar II;

and the variant titles are the following four:

Shāhib Qirāni, Shāhib Qirān Thānī, Thānī Shāhib Qirān,
and Thālith Shāhib Qirān.

I. Shāhib Qirān, صاحب قران.

The simple term Shāhib Qirān is present, unaltered, on the coins of Murād Bakhsh and Jahāndār.

- (a) Murād Bakhsh caused rupees of two different types to be struck at Sūrat in A.H. 1068. Of the rarer type the legend on the Obverse reads:—

مراد شاه غاز

محمد سکندر ثانی

ز صاحب قران جهانی

گرفت

ارث احد

سنه

Muhammad Murād, the victorious King, the Second Alexander,

Took the heritage from (Shāh) Jahān, Lord of the Conjunction.

- (b) Jahāndār approved two distichs for his coins, of which the one given below contains his title Shāhib Qirān.

بؤد سکده بر صده (or زر) چو صاحب قران

جهاندار شاه بادشاه جهان

This legend, with occasional slight variation, is present on both muhrs and rupees struck at Khujista Bunyād, and on the rupees that issued from Etāwā, Dāru-l-Fath Ujjain, Dāru-s-Sarūr Burhānpūr, Barēli, Sūrat, Dāru-l-Khilāfat Shāhjahanābād, and Lakhnau.

[Nādir Shāh is not included among the Emperors of India, but it may here be noted that, during his sanguinary invasion of the country in A.H. 1152, he caused coins to be struck in his name at Dēhli and Ahmadābād, on which he too is styled Shāhib Qirān. They bear the legend:

ہمت سلطان بر سلاطین جهان
شاه شاہان نادر صاحب قرون

II. *Sāhib Qirānī*, صاحب قرانی.

The title 'Lord of Conjunction' with the mere change of قرون to the adjectival قرانی occurs on the coins of *Shāh 'Ālam I* and *Shāh 'Ālam II*.

- (a) Mr. Whitehead in his report on the "Old Coins in the Bahāwalpūr State Toshakhānā" (Num. Supp. XI, p. 333) mentions three muhrs of *Shāh 'Ālam Bahādur I* from the mint *Mustaqirru-l-Khilāfat Akbarābād* bearing the following inscription:—

[مبارک سکہ] صاحب قرانی بہادر عالم گیر تازی

Instead of the first two words مبارک سکہ Mr. Rodgers would read بزر زد سکہ.

The same epithet *Sāhib Qirānī* also occurs on the *Akbarābād rupee*, No. 3, on page 220 in the *Lāhor Museum Catalogue*, which, as Mr. Whitehead points out, has been there erroneously attributed to *Ālamgīr II*. It is, one may confidently affirm, a coin of *Shāh 'Ālam Bahādur I*.

- (b) On both muhrs and rupees of *Shāh 'Ālam II* from *Ahmadnagar-Farrukhābād* and *Dāru-l-Khilāfat Shāhjahānābād*, and on that Emperor's rupees from *Mustaqirru-l-Khilāfat Akbarābād*, *Barēli Qaṭ'*, *Muzaffargarh*, and (perhaps) *Jodhpūr*, we meet with the following legend:

سکہ صاحب قرانی زد زقائید الہ
حامی دین محمد شاه عالم بادشاہ

III. *Sāhib Qirān thānī*, صاحب قران ثانی.

This title, 'the Second Lord of Conjunction,' was adopted by the four Emperors, *Shāh Jahān I*,¹ *Shāh Shujā'*, *Muhammad Shāh*, and *Akbar II*.

¹ *Shāh Jahān I* was the first of the *Mughal Emperors* to have the title *Sāhib Qirān thānī* entered on his coins, but M. Ed. Drouin has adduced interesting evidence which goes to prove that the title was as a matter of fact borne by *Shāh Jahān's* father *Jahāngīr*.

"Les poètes persans contemporains qui étaient à la cour de ce sultān (*Djehān Gīr*.) et célébrèrent son avènement en 1605, disent bien qu'il monta sur le trône au moment où avait lieu la seconde con-jonction (ce qui est faux astronomiquement), mais *Djehān Gīr* n'a jamais pris ce titre sur ses monnaies ni dans ses protocoles. Je dois

- (a) From the very first year of his reign *Shāh Jahān I* introduced this epithet on his coins, and it is to be seen on nearly all the muhrs, rupees, and nithārs that were issued prior to his death. The area of the Reverse of the famous 200-muhr piece exhibits the legend which, with variations as to the arrangement of its constituent words, continued throughout this Emperor's reign to be the normal legend for his coins in gold and silver.

شهاب الدين محمد صاحب قران ثاني
شاه جهان بادشاه غازي

- (b) The two rupees of *Shāh Shujā'*, Nos. 690 and 691 in the British Museum Catalogue, very probably bear in their margin the epithet *Ṣāhib Qirān thānī*. The Catalogue itself gives the words *قران ثاني* as the reading of the right margin of the Reverse of No. 690; and in Num. Supp. VI, pp. 265, 266, Mr. Burn has shown reason for rejecting, as to No. 691, the extremely doubtful rendering "*Jal ūn-ābād*," which Mr. Lane-Poole had ventured to suggest, and for accepting in its stead the reading *Ṣāhib Qirān thānī*.
- (c) On the coins of *Muḥammad Shāh* stood the severely simple legend

سکه مبارک بادشاه غازي محمد شاه

but it would seem that some two years after this Emperor's accession the words *صاحب قران ثاني* were inserted after *مبارک* on the coins, both gold and silver, that issued from the *Shāhjahānābād* mint, a change which was maintained till the close of the reign. The legend as thus altered reads—

سکه مبارک صاحب قران ثاني محمد شاه بادشاه غازي

- (d) *Akbar II's Shāhjahānābād* muhrs and rupees bear a legend identical with the one last recorded, save

“cependant mentionner ce fait que, en 1896, il a été présenté au cabinet de France (qui n'en a pas fait l'acquisition) un rubis rapporté du Turkestan, et sur lequel était gravée une inscription que j'ai cru pouvoir lire de la manière suivante: *Djehān Gīr shāh Akbar shāh ṣāhib-qirān tsāni*, 1019, ce qui prouverait, si la pierre est authentique, que ce souverain aurait pris, avant son fils *Shāh Djehān*, le titre de 'deuxième maître de la conjonction.' ”

Les Symboles astrologiques sur les monnaies de la Perse (*Gazette belge de Numismatique, Bruxelles, 1901*).

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only that the name Akbar is added after Muḥammad. They thus read—

سکه مبارک صاحب قران ثانی محمد اکبر شاه بادشاه غازی

IV. Thānī Sāhib Qirān, ثانی صاحب قران.

This variant form, in which ثانی comes first instead of last, appears on two gold coins of Shāh Jahān I, both of them from the Shāhjahānābād mint. One of these is the 200-muhr piece, on which in the left margin of the Reverse the Emperor is styled

ثانی صاحب قران شاه جهان دین پناه

The other is the beautiful muhr, No. 568 of the British Museum Catalogue, dated 30—1066, which in the margin surrounding the circular area of the Reverse bears the distich

سکه شاه جهان اباد رائج در جهان
جاودان بادا بدام ثانی صاحب قران

V. Thālith Sāhib Qirān, ثالث صاحب قران.

I have seen but a single coin exhibiting this epithet, a Tatta rupee of Farrukh-siyar, dated 1—1125. It is one of the treasures in the cabinet of my kind friend Mr. Framji Jamaspji Thanawala.

The ordinary legend on Farrukh-siyar's coins proclaims the Emperor's title of 'بادشاه بحر و بر', 'Bādshāh of sea and land,' but on this Tatta rupee he is styled instead 'ثالث صاحب قران', 'the Third Lord of Conjunction.' The whole legend reads—

سکه زد از فضل حق برسدیم و زر
ثالث صاحب قران فروخ سیر

NOTE.—In several of the Native States of Rājputānā their rulers have at one time or another issued coins more or less closely resembling those of the contemporary Mughal Emperors. Of these Native State coins the following exhibit the Emperor's name associated with the title Sāhib Qirān thānī:—

Muḥammad Shāh rupees from the mint at Jaisalmēr; Shāh 'Ālam II rupees from Būndī, Bīkānēr, and Qaraulī; and Akbar II rupees from Būndī, Bharatpūr, Dholpūr, and Sawāi-Jaipūr.

GEO. P. TAYLOR.

AHMADĀBĀD :

10th June, 1910.

P.S.—Through the kindness of Mr. R. B. Whitehead, I.C.S., I am able to add a reference to another coin on which the title *Ṣāhib Qirān Ṭhanī* is ascribed to the then regnant Emperor. *Shāh Jahān II* issued from the Tatta mint a coin bearing a couplet which Mr. Whitehead reads as follows:—

سکه زد بر زر با امن امان
صاحب قران ثانی شاه جهان

The Second “Lord of the Conjunction,” *Shāh Jahān*,
Struck coin in gold with security and tranquillity.

G. P. T.

87. MOGHAL MINT TOWNS—FĪROZNAGAR.

In the list upon page 174 of his “Manual,” Dr. O. Codrington places a mark of interrogation against the name of Fīroznagar. I find that it is the new name by which ‘Ālamgīr Aurangzeb disguised Rāechor (Nizām’s Territories), as he did so many other places. In the *M‘āṣir-i-‘Ālamgīrī* (Bibl. Ind.), p. 332, line 2 from foot, we have an entry headed “Capture of Rāechor,” which states that on the 26th Ṣafar [1101 H. Dec. 29, 1689 N.S.], 33rd year, the *Bakhshī-ul-mulk*, Rūḥullah Khān, took the fort of Rāechor, which received the name of Fīroznagar. In 1117 H. (1706), year 50, Chīn Qīlich Khān, Bahādur, was appointed *faujdār* of Fīroznagar vice Yūsuf Khān; *ibid.*, p. 513.

WILLIAM IRVINE.

88. THE QANDAHĀR RUPEE OF MUḤAMMAD SHĀH.

Dr. G. P. Taylor of Ahmadabad writes:—“Just a couple of days after reading your description of a rupee, doubtfully assigned by you¹ to the Qandahār mint, and dated the 30th regnal year of Muḥammad Shāh (N.S. 13: 240), Mr. Qadri, the Oriental Translator to the Bombay Government, very kindly gave me a rupee—normal type—of the same Emperor, on which the mint-name Qandahār is quite clearly written. Its date is the 27th regnal year. It would thus appear that in the 27th and the 30th years of the reign of Muḥammad Shāh (A.H. 1157-1159; A.D. 1744-1746), and presumably from the 27th till the 30th year, coins were issuing from Qandahār in the name of the Dehli Emperor. How is this fact to be explained, if throughout that period the city was under Persian rule? There is another Qandahār, a taluq of Nānder District in the

¹ Numismatic Supplement XIII, J.A.S.B., Vol. VI, No. 4, 1910, p. 240, article 78.